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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 4

Pages: 464-471

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2069

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12780117

Manuscript Accepted: 06-13-2024

Influence of Academic Achievements on High School Students' Personality

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Abstract

This research studies the significant influence of academic achievements on high school students' personality traits, particularly focusing on students in Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Inc. in Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental. This study utilized quantitative research design, using survey questionnaires as data collection tools. Results reveal high levels of both academic achievement with an overall mean of 4.00 and personality traits among the students with an overall mean of 4.19, with motivation exhibiting the highest manifestation in academic achievement at 4.34 and physical attributes at 4.36 in personality traits. Statistical analysis indicates a significant effect of academic achievements on students' personality traits which yielded at 0.00, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. These results give an idea of the need to increase students' academic achievement because it affects their personality development in high school, since there is a chance of implications for educational practices and support services. Furthermore, appreciating this relationship of influence provides an opportunity for more focused interventions that will help in the improvement of academic achievements as well as conditions for personal development among the students. Recommendations such as classroom interventions and maintaining a balance between academic pursuits and personal well being are found to be proven important in this study.

Keywords: *academic achievement, student's personality, effects, quantitative*

Introduction

Personality is considered as the internal processes emerging in combined form of emotions, interpersonal and attitudes that harmonize the reaction, behavior, and interaction with others and as a result becomes the main factor which has considerable impact on behavior of humans (Fayez & Labib, 2016). It is observed that many theorists have classified and measured personality traits and types from diverse viewpoints (Kantan et al., 2017). A personality attribute is the conduct and mindset that a person adopts and demonstrates toward others (Holzman, 2018).

One of psychology's most well-known branches, personality has the greatest potential to impact a person's actions throughout their life. A person's personality is how they perceive themselves; it is their comprehension of how specific behaviors are perceived and demonstrated in the context of their surroundings (Cherry, 2018).

According to Wang et al. (2023), personality, as a stable psychological property, has a significant impact on students' academic performance. According to his studies, pupils' personalities may hinder their learning performance. An individual's personality is situational and dependent on their environment. The Big Five are the most known personality types, despite the fact that there are many others. The acronym OCEAN, which stands for Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism, makes these personality traits easy to identify (Pappas, 2017). Flourishing (2016) stated and emphasized the importance of incorporating and understanding a person's well-being and psychological capabilities. The significance of integrating and comprehending an individual's well-being and psychological skills was underlined by him in his statement.

Academic achievement refers to the knowledge gained, or skill developed in a particular subject, usually measured by test scores or by marks assigned by teachers (Marcenaro et al., 2018). Students who rank high on agreeableness are often more friendly and obedient when dealing with social demands (Vedel & Poropat, 2017). According to Wang et al. (2023), academic accomplishment not only reflects cognitive capacity but also interacts with personality qualities, influencing students' learning experiences.

There are several existing literature on academic achievements and personality studies and how it affects students. However, there is a dearth of details that delve further into the topic. Additionally, the researchers believe that this research is relevant and urgent since it pertains to the present problems that students, particularly Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Inc. students, are experiencing.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to determine the significant influence of academic achievements on the students' personality among high school students. Furthermore, it particularly aimed to attain and fulfill the following specific objectives:

1. To determine the level of academic achievement in terms of:
 - 1.1. academic work;
 - 1.2. motivation;
 - 1.3. academic activities; and
 - 1.4. social activities.

2. To determine the level of students' personality in terms of:
 - 2.1. physical;
 - 2.2. emotional; and
 - 2.3. spiritual.
3. To determine the significant influence of academic achievement on the personality traits of high school students.

Literature Review

Students' Personality

Personality is a multifaceted psychological trait that significantly influences patterns of behavior, as noted by Rochin et al. in 2023. It is a concept that describes how individuals behave in diverse situations, with these behavioral differences carrying real-world consequences.

Physical. The relationship between physical activity and academic performance is a subject of extensive investigation, yielding diverse and at times conflicting results. Recent literature, as highlighted by James et al. (2023), underscores this complexity, reporting varied associations between regular physical activity and academic achievement.

Emotional. The research by Qualez-Robres (2023) examined the impact of Emotional Intelligence (EI) on students' academic performance. It revealed that in well-established education systems, EI showed a strong connection with good academic outcomes. The study suggests that promoting qualities like confidence and kindness in schools can positively influence both academic success and emotional well-being.

Spiritual. In a recent study by Mendoza (2022), the research challenges the misconception that spirituality negatively impacts academic achievement, suggesting instead that spirituality serves as an empowering force for students. This study provides a cautionary note, encouraging students to integrate spirituality into their lives without fear of hampering their academic success.

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement reflects an individual's educational performance and outcomes, shaped by factors like intelligence, motivation, and personality traits (Suvarna et al., 2016).

Academic Work. Academic work refers to the activities and tasks that are part of the educational and scholarly endeavors within an academic setting. This can encompass a wide range of activities and responsibilities, including but not limited to research, writing, teaching, studying, and other related tasks. Excessive homework, however, can lead to reduced free time and increased anxiety and depression levels (Pressman et al., 2015; Courtney & Nix, 2018).

Motivation. Motivation plays a central role in academic achievement, serving as both a predictor and an outcome of educational success. Extensive research has explored the relationships between various motivational factors and academic performance, emphasizing the importance of achievement motives, values, and academic self-concept as predictors of success (Steinmayr, 2014).

Academic Activities. Research indicates that participation in such activities correlates with improved academic performance, elevated test scores, and enhanced grades, all while nurturing vital life skills (Agyekum, 2021). Academic pursuits and engagement in extracurriculars collectively shape a holistic educational experience, influencing both students' academic achievements and personal growth.

Social Activities. Social skills, encompassing effective interaction and relationship-building, are potential indicators of academic achievement (Sharma, et al., 2016). Research shows a complex relationship between social interaction and academics, highlighting the need for a balanced approach to promote academic performance (Ali et al., 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used quantitative research to determine the influence of academic achievements on the students' personality among the students of Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Inc. This was an appropriate method wherein the researchers were able to gather objective data for the statistical analysis.

Participants

The conduct of this study focused on high school students particularly high school students in Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Inc. The study includes a total of 136 from a total population of 180 enrolled high school students of the school year 2023-2024. According to Rulona and Bacasmot in 2023, sample size must reach at least 100 for quantitative research regardless of the designs.

Instruments

The researchers made use of modified downloaded questionnaires. There are two sets of downloaded questionnaires taken from two

different studies. Each questionnaire is set for every individual variable: academic achievements and students' personality. These questionnaires were based on the publicly available instruments from Ilag-Ramos (2016) and Huang (2011), providing a validated foundation for the modifications made. The questionnaires utilized a 5-point Likert scale. The academic achievements questionnaire comprised 28 items, while the students' personality questionnaire consisted of 14 items with response intervals of 4.20-5.00 for Very High, 3.40-4.19 for High, 2.60-3.39 for Moderately High, 1.80-2.59 for Low, and 1.00-1.79 for Very Low. These intervals aid in accurately categorizing and interpreting the respondents' answers.

Procedure

This study employs surveys to gather information on students' academic achievements and personality. The procedure involves obtaining permission from school authorities, securing consent from respondents and their parents, distributing questionnaires, and subsequently collecting, tallying, and analyzing the gathered data to fulfill research objectives.

Data Analysis

This study made use of the following statistical analyses: Mean is used to determine the overall level of academic achievement and students' personality; Standard Deviation quantifies the amount of variation or dispersion in a set of data points; Regression is used to test the significant effects between the variables.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are integral to this study's conduct. Key elements include ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality, with participants granted anonymity through the use of numbers or aliases. The informed consent process, aligned with ethical guidelines, prioritizes clarity, respect, and agreement to participate at the respondent's convenience. Additionally, measures are taken to mitigate risks, emphasize mutual benefits, and prevent plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, conflict of interest, and deceit throughout the research process.

Informed Consent Process. Researchers explain the process's relevance, inclusion criteria, and provide adequate time for respondents to understand and ask questions. Respect for respondents and agreement to answer at their convenience was valued aspects of the study's conduct.

Recruitment. Participants were informed about reporting suspicious behavior, and authorization was sought from the High School Coordinator's office and the School Director/Principal's office for a study among student leaders. Endorsement allowed the researchers to disseminate survey questions to student participants.

Risk. No reported risks for respondents were identified, ensuring their safety during data collection. Mutual benefits for both researchers and participants were emphasized, with an assurance that participation should not have a negative impact.

Benefits. Respondents benefit by expressing themselves freely, exercising freedom of expression, and having time for reflection.

Plagiarism. Strict prohibition against copying others' work for inclusion in the research was emphasized to prevent plagiarism.

Fabrication and Falsification. Absolute transparency was encouraged, strongly discourages falsification, warping, or misstating data to ensure the study's quality and accuracy.

Conflict of Interest and Deceit. Researchers were encouraged to avoid biases, prejudices, and be open to new ideas and criticism, promoting an ethical approach to research.

Results and Discussion

In Table 1 below, the level of academic achievement among high school students in Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc, has a weighted mean of 4.00 with descriptive equivalent of high which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed. Among the four indicators in it (Academic Work, Motivation, Academic Activities, and Social Activities), Motivation got the highest weighted mean of 4.34 with descriptive equivalent of Very High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed. On the other hand, Academic Activities got the lowest weighted mean of 3.77 with descriptive equivalent of High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed.

Table 1. *Academic Achievement*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive level</i>
Academic Work	3.84	High
Motivation	4.34	Very High
Academic Activities	3.77	High
Social Activites	4.06	High
Overall	4.00	High

In Table 2 below, the level of academic students' personality among the high school students of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy Inc. has an overall weighted mean of 4.19 with the descriptive level of high which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed.

Among the three indicators in it (Physical, Emotional, and Spritual), Physical got the highest weighted mean of 4.36 with descriptive equivalent of Very High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed. On the other hand, Emotional got the lowest weighted mean of 3.96 with descriptive equivalent of High which means that the item identified is often manifested/observed.

Table 2. *Students' Personality*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive level</i>
Physical	4.36	Very High
Emotional	3.96	High
Spiritual	4.24	Very High
Overall	4.19	High

In Table 3 below, the results of the test of the influence of academic achievement on students' personality are presented. The relationship is considered significant if the p-value is less than 0.05. Reflected in the table, the p-value for the relationship between academic achievement and students' personality yielded at 0.00. This means that there is a significant relationship between academic achievement and students' personality. For accurate reporting, we present the p-value as $< .001$. Thus, academic achievement is significantly affected by students' personality, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 3. *Regression Analysis of the Variables*

<i>Pair</i>	<i>Variables</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision on Ho</i>
IV and DV	Academic Achievement and Students' Personality	0.00	rejected

In the table 4 below, the sum of squares, degrees of freedom (df), mean square, F-value, and significance (Sig.) for the regression and residuals are presented. The F-value is 0.00, and the p-value is reported as $< .001$, signifying a statistically significant relationship between academic achievement and students' personality, thus leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 4. *ANOVA Results*

<i>Model</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Regression	.003	1	.003	0.00	0.00
Residual	.000	0	0.00		
Total	.003	1			

In Table 5 below, the coefficients for the constant and academic achievement variables are shown along with their standard errors. The standardized coefficient (Beta) for academic achievement is -1.000, indicating a strong negative relationship with the dependent variable. The t-values for both the constant and academic achievement are 0.00, and the p-values are less than $.001$, confirming the statistical significance of the model parameters.

Table 5. *Coefficient Results*

<i>Model</i>	<i>Unstandardized Coefficients</i>		<i>Standardized Coefficients</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>		
(Constant)	6.085	.000		0.00	0.00
Students' Personality	-.471	.000	-1.000	0.00	0.00

Academic Achievement

The level of academic achievement from the responses is high. This means that the level of academic achievement is observed/manifested on many occasions. All of the indicators: academic work; motivation; academic activities; and social activities were described as high.

Academic Work

In this study, academic work is described as high. According to Zheng and Mustapha (2020), academic work is highly manifested through various measures and dimensions of academic achievement. These measures include standardized tests, self-assessment reports, and measurement scales, which evaluate students' cognitive abilities, problem-solving skills, communication skills, and other aspects related to their academic work and performance.

Motivation

In this study, motivation is described as very high. According to Li et al. (2022), motivation is manifested, reinforcing the significance of motivation as a pivotal factor in academic and professional success. Their research provides empirical evidence showcasing the positive relationship between achievement motivation, self-efficacy, academic performance, and employability, thus affirming the observable impact of motivation on various student outcomes. Their study supports that motivation plays a crucial role in driving students' academic achievements and enhancing their employability prospects, thereby bolstering the rationale for investigating and fostering motivation in educational settings.

Academic Activities

In this study, academic activities are described as high. According to Heemskerk and Malmberg (2020), academic activities are manifested. Their research explores engagement levels during instructional activities and tasks within lessons, observing variations in engagement both within and between lessons. They find that engagement levels are influenced by specific academic activities, such as individual tasks, teacher-supported tasks, and assessments. Their findings underscore the observable and influential role of academic activities in shaping student engagement, supporting the notion that such activities are significant factors in educational research.

Social Activities

In this study, social activities are described as high. According to Kassarnig et al. (2018), social activities are prominently observed and manifested. Their research delves into the examination of various social interactions, including calls, text messages, and Facebook activity, to understand their impact on academic performance. Additionally, the study investigates the correlation between personality traits and academic success, further emphasizing the manifestation of social activities in influencing educational outcomes. These findings contribute to the growing body of literature highlighting the significance of social environments in shaping academic achievements.

Students' Personality

The level of students' personality from the responses is high. This means that the level of students' personalities is observed/manifested on many occasions. All indicators, physical, emotional, and spiritual, were described as high.

Physical

In this study, physical activity is described as very high. Kirch et al. (2021) state that physical characteristics are prominently observed and analyzed. Their research delves into the examination of various dimensions related to students' physical attributes, including physical self-concept, achievement motive, sports interest, and motives to be physically active, within the context of physical education. The findings indicate that students exhibit high values on dimensions associated with physical self-concept and sports interest, suggesting that physical aspects play a significant role in shaping students' personalities.

Emotional

In this study, emotions are described as high. According to Karawadia (2023), emotional characteristics are prominently observed and emphasized. The research underscores the significance of emotional intelligence (EQ) in students' academic and future success, highlighting the implementation of mindfulness practices, social-emotional learning (SEL) curriculum, and the cultivation of an environment that values emotional awareness. Their findings contribute to understanding how emotional attributes impact students' development and success, advocating for integrating emotional intelligence as a central component of education systems.

Spiritual

In this study, spirituality is described as very high. According to Mendoza (2022), spirituality is notably observed and emphasized. The research suggests that spirituality, as a part of individuals' lives, can have an impact on academic performance. The study emphasizes that spirituality equips students with focus and discipline in their commitments, highlighting the significant role of spiritual characteristics in shaping students' behaviors and outcomes.

Significance of Effects of Academic Achievement on Students' Personality

The test of the effects of the dependent to the dependent variable revealed that there was a strong and positive significant effect of academic achievement on students' personality among high school students. This implied that any adjustment on the level of academic achievement has a corresponding effect on the level of students' personality

The context of the influence of academic achievement on students' personality is aligned with the findings of the study done by Meyer et al. in 2023. They stated that how well students do in school affects how they behave and feel, depending on what they study and how their grades are measured. Meyer's research shows that what students learn and how they are graded can shape how they act and think.

Furthermore, Wang et al.'s (2023) findings show that academic experiences can potentially shape aspects of personality indirectly through their impact on attitudes, behaviors, and emotional well-being. In addition, Academic achievements can indeed affect students' personalities based on the affective factors mentioned: anxiety, motivation, and self-efficacy (Yang & Wang, 2022). Moreover, Suman et al. (2023) claim that students with strong academic performance also possess strong social abilities. A person's social skills can be enhanced and improved by doing well academically.

Conclusions

The data obtained for this study was analyzed and found to be adequate to support the following conclusions. The level of academic achievement and students' personality are high. This means that the academic achievements and students' personality is observed on

many occasions by high school students.

Moreover, there is a significant effect of academic achievement on students' personality among high school students. Academic achievement positively affects students' personality. This signifies that a student's personality is affected by academic achievement.

Based on the results of the study, the researchers developed several suggestions for students. While academic success is important, it is essential to maintain a balance between academic pursuits and personal well-being. Students are encouraged to prioritize self-care activities such as exercise, hobbies, and spending time with friends and family to foster a well-rounded personality.

Students should seek support from teachers, counselors, or peers if they are struggling academically or emotionally. Building a support network can provide valuable resources and encouragement during challenging times.

Engaging in extracurricular activities and exploring interests outside of academics is also recommended. Participating in hobbies, sports, or clubs can help students develop new skills, interests, and aspects of their personalities. Attention to mental health and well-being is crucial. Students should practice self-care strategies such as mindfulness and relaxation techniques and seek professional help if needed. Mental and emotional health are essential components of overall well-being and personality development.

For future researchers, several recommendations were made. One limitation of this study is the relatively small sample size. Although 141 participants were initially included, only 136 respondents completed the surveys. Due to the large amount of missing data, the sample size was insufficient. Involving more students from various types of schools could make the findings more reliable and help better understand how different educational environments affect students' personalities.

Additionally, examining how students' personalities change over time by studying them for a longer period could have important implications for supporting students' personal development throughout their school years. Instead of relying solely on quantitative data, qualitative approaches such as interviewing students to understand how their grades affect their self-perception and interactions with others could provide valuable insights into the emotional impact of academic performance.

Considering other factors like family income or friendships, which might also play a role in the relationship between grades and personality. Understanding these factors could help develop more targeted interventions to support students. It is also important to consider different cultural contexts since beliefs about school and personality can vary greatly between cultures. This consideration could inform the design of culturally sensitive and inclusive educational programs.

Finally, ensuring that the tests used to measure grades and personality traits are accurate and suitable for all students by validating them with diverse groups could help ensure that assessments are fair and equitable for all students.

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